

FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The study analyses the impact of foreign direct investment on economic development in Nigeria over the period 1980–2019. It employed time series secondary data sourced from the various publications of the Central Bank of Nigeria, the National Bureau of Statistics, and World Development Indicators. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) econometric technique was employed in this study to determine the impact of foreign direct investment on economic development. Findings revealed that economic development is directly related to the inflow of foreign direct investment, and it is also statistically significant at 5% level, which implies that a good performance of the economy is a positive signal for the inflow of foreign direct investment. Although there was a negative relationship between inflation and economic development in the current period and it was statistically significant, the study revealed that there is a positive relationship between foreign direct investment, exchange rate, openness, and economic development, which is in line with apriori expectation. The study further showed that foreign direct investment and openness are among the basic variables that drive economic development. The paper recommended that the government should liberalise the foreign sector, adopt policies that effectively utilise and remove all barriers (arbitrary tariffs, import and export duties, and other levies) to trade, so as to encourage investors, formulate programmes and policies that reduce unemployment, improve the human development index, and reduce the chronic inflation rate to at least a single digit.

Keywords: Economic Development, Foreign Direct Investment, Exchange Rate, Inflation Rate and Openness.

1.1 Introduction

Increased globalisation has captured the attention of not only entrepreneurs and business people but also government officials who are searching for international business advantages in an ever-changing world. The active pursuit of foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria is a signal that the rules of the game have changed under globalisation. The message is clear: "Markets are moving towards international competition, and to prosper, nations need to tap into the resources and opportunities available beyond their borders. To this end, they need not only to attract FDI to their shores but also to engage in outward investment in foreign markets" (Adeleke, Olowe, and Fasesin, 2014).

FDI occupied an important role in the international economy after the Second World War. Theoretical studies on FDI have led to a better understanding of the economic mechanism and the behaviour of economic agents, both at micro and macro levels, allowing the opening of new areas of study in economic theory. To understand foreign direct investment, we must first understand the basic motivations that cause a firm to invest abroad rather than export or outsource production to national firms.

FDI is a direct investment into production or business in a country by an individual or company of another country, either by buying a company in the target country or by expanding the operations of an existing business in that country (Adigwe, Ezeagba, and Udeh, 2015). Foreign direct investment is in contrast to portfolio investment, which is a passive investment in the securities of another country, such as stocks and bonds. The World Bank (1996) conceptualised foreign direct investment (FDI) as an investment that is made to acquire a lasting management interest (usually 10% of voting stock) in an enterprise operating in a country other than that of the investors.

FDI represents a veritable source of foreign exchange and technological transfer, especially to a developing economy like Nigeria. It can be analysed in terms of the inflow of new equity capital (change in foreign share capital), re-invested earnings (unremitted profit), trade and supplier's credit, net inflow of borrowing, and other obligations from the parent company or its affiliates (Nwankwo and Ifejiolor, 2014). Olopoenia (1985) observed that foreign investment could be seen as an additional factor of production and as a supplement to the national savings effort of the capital-importing country. This is meant to relax both the foreign exchange and savings constraints on the rate of growth of output in the recipient country.

Economic growth is the increase in the real output of a nation's goods and services over a particular span of time, whereas economic development is the process of an increase in the level of production in an economy alongside the improvement of

living standards and the advancement of technology sustained over time. In essence, economic development has to do with how the growth is distributed to enhance the standard of living of the citizenry (Onwioduokit, 2020). Given the foregoing, it is necessary to interrogate the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic development in the Nigerian context.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

According to official statistics from UNCTAD, there has been an increase in FDI inflows globally between the years 1980 and 2014. FDI inflows were recorded to be about US\$ 52 million, US\$ 243 million, US\$ 1.2 billion, US\$ 1.3 billion, and US\$ 1.35 billion in the years 1980, 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2014, respectively. Freckleton, Wright, and Craigwell (2012) noted that due to the increase in FDI flows, scholars over the years have been motivated to investigate its determinants and impact on the economy. In Nigeria, the country's net flow of FDI as a percentage of GDP averaged 0.77 percent between 1980 and 1990; 2.04 percent between 1991 and 2000; 2.10 percent from 2001 to 2010; and 1.1 percent between 2011 and 2019, respectively. The GDP per capita growth rate plummeted by 2.4 percent on the average between 1980 and 1990, 0.9 percent between 1991 and 2000, but increased to 5.2 percent between 2001 and 2010, respectively. It averaged 0.5 percent between 2011 and 2019 (World Development Indicators, 2020).

Analysis of Nigeria's inflow of foreign direct investment showed a rise in the late 1960s and 1970s but declined sharply thereafter, thus contributing to the mounting pressures on the capital account. The reduction in foreign direct investment inflow resulted from the decline in fresh equity participation in Nigerian enterprises; thus, the main source of inflow was from unremitted profits. With the liberalisation of the economy in the mid-1980s and the democratisation in 1999, the flow of capital through equity participation in the oil and gas sector, telecommunications, and the privatisation of public enterprises assumed an upward trend. The sustained rise in FDI inflows into the country resulted from macroeconomic stability, robust external reserves, favourable rating by the international rating agencies, delisting of the country by the Financial Action Task Force (FATF), as well as fiscal prudence and transparency in the allocation of new oil blocks by the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) (Freckleton et al. 2012). Portfolio investment inflows, which had hitherto remained low, witnessed a substantial increase in demand from 2004 to 2006 owing to investment opportunities presented by the privatisation of public utilities and the consolidation of the financial sector under the NEEDS programme. With further liberalization of the capital accounts,

foreign portfolio investors are attracted to high returns on investments in the money market (National Planning Commission, 2005).

Nigeria slumped from its number one position in 2012 to achieve \$5.61 billion in FDI inflows in 2013, coming third behind Mozambique and South Africa (UNCTAD, 2013). Most scholars believe that FDI inflow has a direct impact on foreign exchange reserves, while others hold that FDI is mainly invested in the form of physical capital and technology and therefore does not directly contribute to foreign exchange reserve accumulation.

It is based on this backdrop that this study focused on finding the causal relationship between foreign direct investment and economic development. The study also examined the impact of foreign direct investment on the economic development of Nigeria. In line with this position, the study attempted to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the impact of foreign direct investment on economic development in Nigeria?
2. What is the causal relationship between foreign direct investment and economic development in Nigeria?
3. Is there any long-run relationship between foreign direct investment and economic development in Nigeria?

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of foreign direct investment on economic development in Nigeria.

2.1 Review of Literature

2.1.1 Economic development

Economic development is a wider concept than economic growth. It is taken to mean growth plus change. It is related to qualitative changes in economic wants, goods, incentives, institutions, productivity, knowledge, or the upward movement of the entire social system. It describes the underlying determinants of growth, such as technological and structural changes. In fact, economic development embraces both growth and non-growth dimensions. An economy can grow, but it may not develop because poverty, unemployment, and inequalities may continue to persist due to the absence of technological and structural changes (Jhingan, 2007).

Economic development is concerned with rising output trends and enhancements in the social and political structures of the people. Proponents of the dependency model contend that economic development refers to the problems of

underdeveloped countries and economic growth to those of developed countries. Maddison (1970) made the distinction between the two terms in this sense when he wrote: "The rising of income levels is generally called economic growth in rich countries, and in poor ones, it is called economic development." In this study, macroeconomic indicators such as per capita gross domestic product, unemployment, and the human development index (HDI) will be used as measures of economic development.

2.1.2 Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

Foreign direct investment (FDI) is a direct investment into production or business in a country by an individual or company of another country, either by buying a company in the target country or by expanding the operations of an existing business in that country. Foreign direct investment is in contrast to portfolio investment, which is a passive investment in the securities of another country, such as stocks and bonds (Adeleke et al., 2014).

The World Bank (1996) conceptualised foreign direct investment (FDI) as an investment that is made to acquire a lasting management interest (usually 10% of voting stock) in an enterprise operating in a country other than that of the investors. According to Umoh (2012), foreign direct investment (FDI) is the most important external finance for most developing countries. This arises from its strategic role in bringing in other complementary development elements like technology, technical skills, and employment, among others. Unfortunately, Africa's share of FDI to developing countries dropped from 25% in the early 1970's to about 5% in the year 2000 (World Bank, 2001). One of the most frequently cited reasons for Africa's declining ability to attract FDI is the risk of its business environment. The most important aspect of this risk is the pervasive corruption. The World Bank puts it succinctly by noting that most investors regard Africa as a bad business address, hence the lack of interest. Thus, institutionalised corruption deprives the continent of the much-needed external development inputs to attract FDI.

2.2 Theoretical framework:

This study is based on the two-gap model

2.2.1 The two-gap theory

The two-gap theory provides a more rigorous and practical foundation for foreign direct investment. The two-gap theory was developed by McKinnon in 1964. The theory states that given the importance of financial capital in economic development, developing

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countries may be constrained by the unavailability of adequate resources to prosecute its development programmes. It identifies two gaps that may exist: the savings gap and the foreign exchange gap because of low income and hence low savings. Once this occurs, savings rate S will lag behind a target rate, say S^* . Moreover, given the high debt burden of less developed countries and their dependence on primary exports, characterised by price instability, quantity instability, or both, a foreign exchange gap may result because the country does not have enough foreign exchange earnings to pay for its imports. Foreign capital inflow appears to be the most viable option to finance the gap.

Two- Gaps Theory, Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Development

Investigations on the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth or sustainable economic development have been conducted by some scholars using Harrod (1948) and Domar (1957) two-gap growth theory. For instance, Voica *et al.* (2015) examined the nexus between FDI and sustainable development using the two-gap model and found several links to achieving the SDGs through investments. The study also found the importance of FDI, specifically for environmental projects, to improve greenhouse effects along with promoting social and economic goals. Flora and Agrawal (2017) revealed a robust causal linkage running from FDI to enhanced skilled labour wages, advanced technology, and sustainable development. Melane-Lavado *et al.* (2018) explored innovative ways for sustainable development and identified a positive impact of FDI based on small and medium organisations related to technology supply.

FDI also influences the environment and the economic components of sustainable development. Even a favourable effect of FDI on poverty was identified by Gohou and Soumare (2012) in Africa. However, the impact was higher in poor regions as compared to wealthier regions. Agyemang *et al.* (2019) examined the link between country-level corporate governance and FDI in African economies from 2009 to 2015. The authors used annual time series data from 40 African countries and deployed the generalised system method of moments (GMM) to explore a correlation between country-level corporate governance and FDI. The authors found that African economies comprised of firms with high-level ethical values that tend to experience more significant FDI inflows than those lacking the same. Djokoto *et al.* (2012) evaluated domestic and foreign direct investment in the Ghanaian agricultural sector. They used time-series data from 1976 to 2007 and revealed that FDI into the Ghanaian agricultural sector crowd-in domestic investment and found that FDI does not have a significant impact on the Ghanaian agricultural sector. Alfaro (2017) investigated how and when FDI promotes growth in emerging markets. The study noted that the mechanism by

which multinational activities might build direct impacts and externalities on economies and the role complementing domestic environment also referred to as “absorptive capacities” that enable a nation to harvest the gains of FDI by focusing on factor market reallocation effects and the interaction between domestic and foreign firms. Srinivasan et al. (2011) conducted an empirical investigation of FDI inflows and growth in the economies of SAARC. The study employed Johansen's cointegration test to determine the long-run relationship between FDI and GDP for the SAARC economies under investigation, namely, Bangladesh, India, the Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka, and found a positive relationship between both variables within the period of investigation. Shuaib et al. (2015) used the Harrod (1948) and Domar (1957) two-gap model to explore the effects of FDI on the growth of the Nigerian economy using time series data from 1981 to 2013. The study found that there is no significant relationship between FDI and economic growth in Nigeria.

2.3 Empirical Literature

2.3.1 Studies on foreign investment and economic development.

Dinh, Vo 2, & Nguyen (2019), in their study on Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Growth in the Short Run and Long Run: Empirical Evidence from Developing Countries, the lower-middle-income group in 2000–2014, employed various econometric methods such as the panel-based unit root test, Johansen cointegration test, Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), and Fully Modified OLS (FMOLS) to ensure the robustness of the findings. The results of this study show that FDI helps stimulate economic growth in the long run, although it has a negative impact in the short run for the countries in this study. Other macroeconomic factors also play an important role in explaining economic growth in these countries. Money supply has a positive effect on growth in the short run, while total credit for the private sector has a negative effect. In addition, long-run economic growth is driven by money supply, human capital, total domestic investment, and domestic credit for the private sector. Based on these results, recommendations for the governments of these countries have been developed.

Giwa, George, Okodua, and Adediran (2020) used the robust GMM estimation method to look at how foreign direct investment affects Nigeria's real economic growth and what that means for Sustainable Development Goal 17. This method fixed the issues of endogeneity and autocorrelation that come up with ordinary least squares. The study found that labour quality has a positive and significant effect on RGDP, in line with theory. Equally, it was noted that capital intensity displayed a significant negative effect on RGDP in Nigeria. This study therefore recommends that policymakers in Nigeria

should incorporate into their broad policy, improvement in capital intensity as a bedrock to growing the economy through FDI spillover effects.

Adegboye, Osabohien, Olokoyo, Matthew, and Adediran's (2020) studies on institutional quality, foreign direct investment, and economic development in sub-Saharan Africa employed pooled data for 30 SSA countries for the period between 2000 and 2018. The analysis method used was the fixed and random effect regression model utilised to estimate the effect of foreign capital on economic development with considerations for the quality of institutions in the developing SSA sub-region of Africa. This study reveals that foreign capital inflow is crucial for economic development in the SSA sub-region of Africa. The quality of institutions as determining factors also affected the level of inflow of FDI to the host SSA sub-region, which resulted in the underutilization of domestic resources and hence the abnormal development of domestic sector investment. The study recommends that the government of the host SSA subregion needs to consider the degree of institutional quality to encourage further FDI inflows. To afford the maximal benefit of FDI in the development of the host domestic sector and to guard the industry that foreign investment flows into carefully, it is expedient, therefore, that domestic investment be enhanced to ensure that dependence on foreign capital inflow continues to decline as income increases.

In related development studies conducted by Ugwuanyi, Efanga, and Ogochukwu (2020) on the impact of foreign direct investment on economic development in Nigeria between 1981 and 2018, using data elicited from the World Bank Data Base—World Developmental Indicators of 2018 and the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin of 2018, gross fixed capital formation was employed as a proxy for economic development in Nigeria and exchange rate as a controlled variable, while data on foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria was adopted as the explanatory variable. The study employed the auto-regressive distributed lag (ARDL) model to analyse data; other diagnostic tests such as the stability test, auto-correlation test, heteroskedasticity test, and Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test were also carried out, and they confirmed the validity and reliability of the model employed. The inferential results pointed out that foreign direct investment impacted positively but insignificantly on economic development in Nigeria between 1981 and 2018. These results also conform to a priori economic expectations. The study recommended that the government of Nigeria should provide an enabling environment that will be conducive for businesses so as to attract additional inflows of foreign direct investment. The government can provide an enabling business environment by providing a steady supply of electricity, ameliorating or exterminating insurgent activities in the country, and restoring the confidence of investors. When this is done, the volume of foreign direct

investment into Nigeria will increase, which will enhance exports, thereby reducing the exchange rate.

Similarly, Iheanachor and Ozegbe (2021), who explored the contribution of foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows to the sustainable development of the Nigerian and Ghanaian economies, were prompted by the apparent evidence of rising FDI inflows in the last two decades, which has failed to improve both nations' sustainable development drive significantly. The study employed the ordinary least squares (OLS) econometric technique to test the effect of FDI inflows on sustainable development indicators using annual time series data from 2000 to 2018 obtained from both countries' World Development Indicators (WDI) for the period covering the Millennium Development Goals (MDG) era and the earlier stages of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of the United Nations (UN). The findings revealed that Ghana performed better than Nigeria on social sustainability, measured in terms of education and healthcare indicators. However, on environmental and economic sustainability, Nigeria fared better. A percentage increase in FDI inflow to both countries enhances economic growth and economic sustainability by 0.30 percent. However, the study indicated that the positive impact is statistically insignificant. This reveals that the difference in economic growth and economic sustainability in both countries is not accounted for by FDI.

3.1 Method

To achieve the stated objective, the study used information and data from secondary sources, and therefore time series data sourced from various publications of the Central Bank of Nigeria, such as the Statistical Bulletin, Annual Reports, and Statement of Accounts. The models for this study were estimated using data on foreign direct investment (FDI) and some macro-economic indicators, which include: per capita gross domestic products (PCGDP), exchange rate (EXCHR), inflation rate (INFLA), trade openness (OPEN), interest rate (INTR), and government expenditure (GEXP) for the period 1980–2019.

The autoregressive distribution lag technique is employed in this study to determine the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic development within the specified time frame.

3.1 Model Specification:

The model for this study is as specified below

3.1.1 FDI and Economic development equation:

The model for FDI and economic development equation for this study is given as:

$$PCGDP = F(FDI, OPEN, EXCHR, INFLR, HDI, UNEM, INTR) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The econometric form of the model is given as:

$$PCGDP_t = b_0 + b_1FDI_t + b_2OPEN_t + b_3EXCHR_t + b_4INFLR_t + b_5HDI_t + b_6UNEM_t + b_7INTR_t U_t \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Linearizing it we will have:

$$\log PCGDP_t = \log b_0 + b_1 \log FDI_t + b_2 \log OPEN_t + b_3 \log EXCHR_t + b_4 \log INFL_t + b_5 \log HDI_t + b_6 \log UNEM_t + b_7 \log INTR_t U_t \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

PCGDP – Per Capita Gross Domestic Product growth in time t

FDI – Foreign Direct Investment in time t

OPEN – Openness in time t

EXCHR – Exchange Rate in time t

INFL – Inflation Rate in time t

UNEM – Unemployment rate in time

INTRt – interest rate in time t

Ut – Error term

Appriori Expectation shows that $b_1 > 0, b_2 > 0, b_3 > 0, b_4 < 0, b_5 > 0,$ and $b_6 < 0, b_7 < 0$

3.1.3 Model estimation procedure

The ADF and PP unit root test was adopted to determine the order of integration while the causality test seeks to detect the direction of causality. Co-integration test was used to determine the existence of long-run equilibrium relationship (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). If the order of integration of the time series variables are of order one (i.e., I (1)), then Johansen co-integration test is suitable; but if the order of integration is a combination of order zero and one (i.e., I (0) and I (1)), ARDL-bounds co-integration test procedure is suitable. This study used both the Johansen and ARDL tests for co-integration. ARDL was used for inclusive growth and trade, and error correction mechanism was used for the equation. The analytical software of the study is E-Views 9 software.

4.1 Results and Discussion

4.1.1 Long run dynamic result of FDI and economic development equation

4.1a Dependent variable: D (PCGDPR)

Variable	Coefficien			
	t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	5.324640	27.454849	0.193942	0.8476
FDI	-0.000501	0.000709	-0.706439	0.4856
OPEN	-0.476380	0.692440	-0.687973	0.4969
EXCHR	0.029098	0.051621	0.563689	0.5773
INFLA	-0.170786	0.081392	-2.098322	0.0447
INTR	0.967607	0.308164	3.139905	0.0039
CointEq(-1)	-0.666191	0.144879	-4.598249	0.0001

4.1.3 Foreign direct investment and economic development equation results. long run coefficients of foreign direct investment and economic development equation

The long run equation for foreign direct investment is presented in Table 4.1a. From the outcomes and in contravention of theoretical expectations, an inverse relationship exists between foreign direct investment and the income per capita growth rate in Nigeria at the current period. The value of the coefficient of -0.000501 implies that a reduction in foreign direct investment by 1 percent will decrease per capita income growth by -50.1 percent, ceteris paribus. The p-value indicates that FDI is statistically insignificant. This simply means that the effect of FDI on GDP per capita growth in the current period is minimal, showing that the influence on GDP is not enough to bring about the necessary change in GDP. According to the result, a rise in FDI will positively exhibit a long run association with PCGDP in the country.

The coefficient of -0.476380 for openness at the current period shows that a 1 percent decrease in openness in the long run will lead to a -47.63 percent decrease in per capita income (PCGDPR), showing a negative association between openness and income at the current period. The magnitude of the coefficient of openness at the current period shows that a one percent decrease in openness ratio in the long run will lead to a decrease of -47.63 percent in per capita income growth (PCGDPR). This is inconsistent with theory. The insignificance of the variable openness at the current period indicated by the P-value signifies that although openness is important in influencing the rate of per capita income in Nigeria, it is statistically insignificant at the current period to bring about the necessary change in PCGDP.

The result of the bound test at upper bound of 3.79 shows that the long run effect of the per capita gross domestic product (PCGDP) on GDP by the current period has a positive impact on the present PCGDP, with a ratio of 3.79 indicating an increase in FDI will lead to a simultaneous increase in per capita GDP growth. According to the result of the study, a decrease in the ratio of foreign direct investment (FDI) squared (PCGDP) by one percent will induce a reduction in income by -0.0005 percent, ceteris paribus. The statistical insignificance of the variable (-0.706439) indicates that, although it is an essential variable that affects income growth in Nigeria, its effect at the current period is not sufficient to generate the necessary change in PCGDP. It was equally revealed that a positive relationship exists between the exchange rate and per capita GDP growth in the current period. It was established that a 1 percent increase in the exchange rate will bring about a 29.10 percent increase in FDI and PCGDP growth in the current period, respectively. It is statistically insignificant for the current period. Openness (OPEN) was negatively signed and was not in conformity with a priori expectations. It shows that a 1 percent increase in openness to GDP ratio will lead to a decrease in per capita GDP by -0.47 percent.

Exchange rate became positively related to per capita income after a period lag, while foreign direct investment was directly related to per capita income after a period lag. The exchange rate (EXCHR) and foreign direct investment (FDI) coefficients show that a 1% rise in either of these variables will cause the per capita GDP growth rate (PCGDP) to fall by 0.029 for exchange rate (EXCHR) and -0.0005 for FDI during the same time period. With the cointegration coefficient of 0.66 for PCGDP, there is a long run relationship among the variables, or there is cointegration because the cointegrating coefficient of -0.66 is negative and statistically significant at the 5% level of significance.

4.1.2 Short run dynamics result of foreign direct investment and economic development equation

Table 4.1b: Short Dynamics or Coefficient of FDI and Economic Development Conditional Error Correction Regression

Variable	Coefficien			
	t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(FDI)	0.000123	0.000300	0.411621	0.6836
D(OPEN)	0.726000	0.807946	0.898575	0.3763
D(EXCHR)	-0.053469	0.041187	-1.298199	0.2044
D(INFLA)	-0.113776	0.050220	-2.265563	0.0311
D(INTR)	0.644611	0.184818	3.487818	0.0016
CointEq(-1)	-0.666191	0.144879	-4.598249	0.0001

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024).

The dynamic results of the short run foreign direct investment - economic development equations are presented in Table 4.1b. From the table, there exists a positive relationship between OPEN/GDP at the current period. This is in line with theoretical expectations. The coefficient of OPEN at the current period is statistically insignificant, implying that although FDI is an essential variable that influences income growth in the country, its influence at the current period is not enough to bring about the necessary change in GDP. It was shown that a 1 percent rise in the OPEN/GDP ratio in the short run will cause an increase in income growth of 72.60 percent in the current period. This is in line with the finding of Ajayi (2003), who opined that all the capital inflow into the Nigerian economy from other countries increases FDI, which is the most promising policy due to its potential in dealing with the problems of the savings gap, shortage of technology, and needed skills. The result indicates a positive relationship between FDI/GDP squared (INTR) and income per capita growth in Nigeria. The p-value of 3.487818 for INTR suggests that it is statistically significant. The coefficient of 0.644611 for INTR shows that a 1% increase in INTR will cause a 64.46 percent increase in FDI.

The inflation rate (INFL), with a coefficient estimate of -0.113776 at current period, indicates that the inflation rate contributes negatively to economic development. As the inflation rate increases by 1 percent, economic development decreases by about 0.11 percent. This is a call for a reduction in the inflation rate.

FDI has a positive coefficient of 0.000123 in the short run and is statistically insignificant at 5 percent alpha level. This is in consonance with economic theory, as the

prior condition has been met. The implication of this result is that foreign direct investment (FDI) did not add much to the economic development of Nigeria in the period under review.

The R-squared value of 0.67 and the adjusted R-squared of 0.60 show that 67 percent of the total variation in the PCGDP is explained by the independent variables, and about 33 percent was unexplained, which may be accounted for by other factors not included in the model. The F-statistical value of 13.85 shows that all the variables in the model are together statistically significant, which means that the model has a good fit, while the D-W value of 2.27 shows no presence of autocorrelation in the model. Therefore, the results can be used for economic forecasting and economic policy. There is a cointegrating relationship among the variables in the estimated or regression model, and the error correction mechanism has the correct sign and size. The ECM coefficient (-0.666191) indicates that it takes about 66.61 percent for the short run disequilibrium to adjust to the long equilibrium within a year. The t-statistics of -4.598249 shows that the error correction term is statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

4.2 Discussion

The long and short run equations of foreign direct investment and economic development show a negative relationship between foreign direct investment, openness, and economic development. This is in contravention to theoretical expectations. An inverse relationship exists between foreign direct investment and the income per capita growth rate in Nigeria at the current period.

Moreso, positive, negative, and significant relationships were found between the exchange rate, interest rate, and economic development in both the long and short run. This is in line with the views of Dinh, Vo 2, & Nguyen (2019) and Giwa, George, Okodua, and Adediran (2020), who studied the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic development in India and Nigeria. The inferential results pointed out that foreign direct investment impacted positively but insignificantly on economic development in Nigeria between 1981 and 2018. These results also conform to a priori economic expectations. The study recommended that the government of Nigeria should provide an enabling environment that will be conducive for businesses so as to attract additional inflows of foreign direct investment. The government can provide an enabling business environment by providing a steady supply of electricity, ameliorating or exterminating insurgent activities in the country, and restoring the confidence of investors to come into Nigeria and invest. When this is done, the volume of foreign direct investment into Nigeria will increase, enhancing exports and thereby reducing the exchange rate.

5.1 Conclusion

The study examined the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic development in Nigeria from 1980–2019, adopting the autoregressive distributive lag model. The study observed that changes in the ratios of foreign direct investment to GDP affect economic development in Nigeria. In addition, the study revealed a negative relationship between inflation and GDP and the human development index to GDP squared, implying that these ratios are mostly above the threshold levels. It means that the continuous accumulation of high inflation with a worsening unemployment rate increases the discomfort index. This scenario is compounded by poor management of foreign direct investment accumulation, a high interest and inflation rate, an unstable exchange rate, inadequate capital formation, and unfavourable loan terms, making it extremely difficult to service the mounting external debt obligations. However, human development index variables such as education and infrastructural development have a greater impact on economic development than inflation in Nigeria. Low external debt stock impacted positively and significantly on foreign direct investment as well as economic development. The result of the evaluation of the relationship between openness and economic development was positive and significant. This confirms the role of openness in sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Lastly, foreign direct investment equations and depreciation in the exchange rate will lead to a reduction in capital accumulation in Nigeria. However, a reduction in foreign direct investment will worsen poverty and unemployment in the country.

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